

Wearable device for personalized EMG feedback-based treatments

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ABSTRACT

Curative effects of electromyography (EMG) feedback in treatment of various conditions and/or recovery after injuries have been earlier reported. However, wider application on EMG feedback is somehow limited due to the overall price of such systems and limited availability outside of the specialized treatment centers. Development of a personalized device for EMG feedback would be of great importance for home recovery after stroke or injuries, achieving better success in fitness and improving biofeedback-based treatments of conditions such as urinary incontinence. Despite extensive research on EMG signal collection, there is a lack of focus on *in-situ* EMG analysis that considers the intensity and duration of muscle activities. This gap presents the motivation for our research. In this paper, we present a methodology for the realization of wearable, rechargeable battery-powered, small-sized (90 mm × 60 mm) electronic device for recording two EMG channels (12-bits resolution, sampling frequency up to 1.6 kHz) with Bluetooth Low Energy connectivity to a smartphone. An average current consumption of 20.5 mA was experimentally determined, suggesting that multiday continuous functionality is possible. Advancing the state of the art, we propose a cross-correlation-based algorithm for *in-situ* dynamical computing and evaluation of muscle activation levels. This algorithm can determine if the muscle follows a predefined profile of contractions/relaxations (as needed for the treatment) and indicate if two muscles in a specific exercise were or were not engaged in proper time and with the proper intensity. The performed simulation analysis showed that the proposed approach exhibited shorter processing time compared to Morlet Wavelet Transform and Dynamic Time Warping. Finally, experimental work with five human volunteers demonstrated the reliability in EMG acquisition and signal processing. Therefore, the main contribution of this work is a cost-effective, small-sized, customizable EMG recording system with an efficient cross-correlation-based algorithm for *in-situ* EMG collection and processing.

1. Introduction

The electromyography (EMG) feedback is a technique that involves recording of EMG signals and their visualization to the subject with the aim of providing real-time information about their muscle activity (contractions/relaxations) and guidance in exercise [1]. It is also important in biomechanics research [2,3]. EMG feedback is very useful for human-robot interaction systems [4] and the control of a hybrid upper-limb orthosis [5], where it can be used as a control input. It is also valuable for robotic devices used in rehabilitation [6], and the treatment of various conditions such as musculoskeletal pain disorders [1], recovery of motor function after stroke [7–10], knee osteoarthritis [11], patellofemoral pain syndrome [12], chronic back pain [13], and urinary incontinence (UI) [14–16], among others. Rehabilitation outcomes of above mentioned conditions are more likely to be more positive when EMG biofeedback is included, as shown in cases of improved arm

function after stroke [9]. Moreover, the findings from Ref. [10] suggest that EMG biofeedback outperforms conventional therapy in enhancing muscle strength for ankle dorsiflexion. Another study discovered that within three weeks, EMG biofeedback could modify the activity levels of the vastus medialis and lateralis in normal subjects, which is considerably shorter than regular exercise regimes [12]. In addition to that, the problem of UI is also widely spread [17].

The main limitations of EMG feedback in treatments of the above-mentioned conditions are its high price and limited availability, typically found only in specialized healthcare centers. Additionally, users are required to visit hospitals for treatment sessions, which can be inconvenient. Treatments usually last for a few weeks, imposing significant financial burdens on patients who do not reside near equipped hospitals, such as those in rural areas. On the other hand, muscle exercises without feedback have demonstrated poor efficiency, especially among beginners. For example, about 66 % of women expressed

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confidence in their ability to perform pelvic floor exercises correctly. However, due to potential discrepancies between perception and actual performance, it is likely that a portion of them may not be executing these exercises accurately [18].

Despite all the research that has been done to develop methods to collect EMG signals [19–23], very little or no attention is devoted to *in-situ* EMG analysis without PC-based stations about muscle activities with respect to their intensity and duration of activity, as we discussed within state-of-the-art overview in Section 2. The significance of a system that integrates *in-situ* EMG collection and processing lies in its potential to provide users with immediate feedback about their muscle responses during various activities. This feedback can be important for individuals undergoing recovery after injuries, as it enables them to monitor progress and adjust rehabilitation exercises accordingly. Additionally, it can enable patients to actively participate in their rehabilitation process and learn to modulate their muscle activity patterns.

The main motivation of this work is to address an identified research gap with the development of an electronic device for wearable, battery-powered, small-sized dual EMG recordings with Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) connectivity to smartphones, and an algorithm for *in-situ* dynamical computing of cross-correlation of two signals (two EMG sources or evaluation of whether a single muscle follows a predefined profile of contractions/relaxations). As it will be further discussed in the body text of the manuscript, the main contributions of our work are: (1) it is designed as a generic system for EMG recordings, aiming to be cost-effective without compromising on functionality or performance, (2) our device offers a personalized solution that can be tailored to individual needs, addressing the limited customization options or accessibility found in the majority of commercial systems, which are often confined to specialized treatment centers, (3) our proposed signal processing algorithm, based on the cross-correlation, demonstrates shorter processing time, better selectivity, and accuracy in determining similarity in EMG signals compared to Morlet Wavelet Transform and Dynamic Time Warping, and (4) our experimental results with human volunteers validate the effectiveness of our system in accurately capturing EMG signals and processing them in real-time. The developed device holds significant potential for applications in recovery after injuries, achieving better success in fitness, and biofeedback-based treatments.

2. State of the art

A method for detecting wrist-hand movements using EMG signals from randomly placed sensors on the forearm was presented in Ref. [20]. The study utilized eight time-domain features used to characterize the EMG signals, with real-time operation on an embedded ARM Cortex-A53 processor. The authors achieved a 90 % reduction in execution time compared to the traditional methods. However, the Myo Armband used for data acquisition has connectivity for 8 EMG sensors with the sampling frequency of 200 Hz and 8-bit ADC resolution.

The system presented in Ref. [21] employed a 3D electromagnetic positioning system consisting of 11 small-sized electromagnetic sensors mounted on a glove to capture hand and finger positions in real time. The system also recorded associated EMG signals from the forearm muscles. A customized double-channel EMG measurement device was developed, with a PC sound card used as the ADC. A Graphical User Interface (GUI) was developed to visualize the hand movement in real time, providing visual EMG-based feedback to users on how to control a prosthetic hand. However, the accuracy of the system depends on proper calibration and normalization of EMG data to eliminate artifacts. The complexity of the system and the need for precise sensor placement may limit its practical applicability for everyday use.

On the other hand, certain biofeedback systems necessitate a full-size computer to display patient feedback, as they rely on MATLAB-based signal processing and GUI [24], rendering their functionality inaccessible for home use [24,25]. Some systems are based on commercial

hardware, such as *mBraintrain* (with a sampling frequency of up to 500 Hz [24]), which also introduces an issue of collecting raw EMG signals that might be used for research or machine learning procedures.

Surface electrodes, BLE connectivity (managed by an Android app), a small-sized battery with a 10-bit ADC, and an ASIC (Application-Specific Integrated Circuit) were deployed to monitor muscle fatigue by analyzing muscle fibre conduction velocity [26]. However, the capacity of the available EEPROM limits data storage, which might require frequent data transfers to an external device for prolonged monitoring.

Monitoring of vital signs was achieved by utilizing various body sensor nodes, including EMG [27]. The advantage of the proposed cloud-based architecture is real-time access to medical records for doctors and patients. However, cloud-based EMG data processing requires secure data transmission and storage, as well as very efficient handling and processing of large volumes of data to avoid latency and ensure reliability.

Another example of ASIC-based processing of EMG data is in facial expression monitoring [28]. Additional technological features include a BLE and a 10-bit ADC. The device is powered by a lithium-polymer battery. Despite its reported advanced capabilities, the device faces limitations such as 128 kB EEPROM-based data storage and constrained battery life, as well as the complexity of integrating multiple components for real-time processing and data management.

The work authored by Yassin et al. includes a handheld device for single channel sEMG data collection and integration with smartphone applications for both the patient and the physiotherapist. The device features an EMG circuit that acquires signals from the patient's muscles (although the actual ADC sampling rate and resolution are not reported), a microcontroller (MCU)-based on ARM Cortex 32-bit M3 architecture, a Bluetooth module for communication, and a lithium-polymer battery (with no reported battery charger). The system allows real-time monitoring and control of rehabilitation sessions through a Google Firebase database. However, the system has limitations, such as requiring experienced personnel to interpret EMG signals and potential data transfer security issues [29].

A single channel EMG system for muscle fatigue detection is recently presented in Ref. [30]. It includes AD8237 instrumentation amplifier, as well as EYSKJNZWB module that integrates ADC (12-bits at sampling frequency of 2.5 kHz) and BLE data transfer to the smartphone with customized application. However, it lacks *in-situ* muscle similarity index calculation or evaluation of whether the user follows the predefined sequence of exercises (properly timed contractions and relaxations). The overall dimensions of the system are 35 mm × 11 mm × 53 mm.

The electronics system for the EMG-based biofeedback described in Ref. [31] include the use of surface electrodes to acquire the EMG signal, which is then filtered and digitized using a 14-bit ADC at a sampling rate of 10 kHz (NI USB 6009-based). The digitized signal undergoes further digital processing, including low-pass filtering with a 50-point moving average and conversion to absolute values for muscle effort estimation. However, the signal processing of the presented system is MATLAB-based, which limits portability and use on users' PCs without a specialized GUI. Battery-powered operation, wireless data transfer to the mobile phone, and a smartphone application are not reported.

The EMG patch designed for real-time monitoring of muscle fatigue includes an analog circuit, an ARM Cortex-M4 MCU unit, a BLE module, a power circuit, and an alarm system. The analog circuit utilizes an instrument amplifier and a series of Butterworth filters to remove noise. The MCU measures the median frequency (MF) of the EMG signal in real-time, which shifts to a lower frequency as muscle fatigue sets in. The BLE module transmits these real-time MF values to a smartphone or notebook for monitoring and analysis [32].

The wearable EMG/ECG sensor-based monitoring system proposed in Ref. [33] focuses on training for upper limb rehabilitation. The system comprises three main components: a wearable monitoring device prototype with dual channel ECG/EMG sensors, a soft robotic glove device, and a software platform (running on a smartphone or laptop). Data

exchange is achieved via BLE. The hardware platform uses the STM32L152 chip, precision instrumentation amplifiers (AD8221) and 12-bits ADC to collect and process EMG signals from the forearm muscles. However, the system faces limitations such as the complexity and power consumption of the algorithm, which makes real-time implementation challenging.

3. Materials and methods

3.1. Overall structure and purpose of the proposed system

The main design goal of our system is to implement EMG analog front end (EMG AFE) for reliable real-time data collection from two

independent channels with muscle response similarity indication. Our intention is to provide a practical guide with detailed explanations for the implementation of EMG feedback systems in real-world environments. We also incorporated current technological solutions and our innovative ideas in reliable EMG signal processing, based on *in-situ* cross-correlation calculation. *In-situ* cross-correlation calculation can be used as the indicator if muscles have same/different response while a specific exercise is performed, or if, in a recovery treatment, the targeted profile is successfully followed with the muscle of interest. Additionally, the proposed device is designed to be wearable, low-sized, battery-powered and to have wireless connectivity (BLE) with the in-house developed smartphone application. To enhance portability and reduce the waste of non-rechargeable batteries, the charger and battery

Fig. 1. (a) Electrical schematic of the proposed system, (b) Bode plots and structures of implemented filters, (c) the proposed processing of EMG signals, (d) the structure of the smartphone application, and (e) the pseudo-code presentation of the microcontroller programming code.

monitoring circuit for proposed Lithium-Polymer (Li-Po) battery are included.

3.2. Electrical schematic of the proposed system

Muscle under test is connected to the system using the three-electrode system. Needle EMG electrodes are sometimes preferred over surface EMG (sEMG) electrodes for diagnostic purposes due to their targeted nature, but they also carry potential risks of pain, bleeding, and infection, especially in home applications. sEMG measurements are typically performed with three or five electrodes. While the five-electrode setup offers higher precision and detailed information about muscle activity compared to the simpler three-electrode setup, it also consumes more materials, requires more space for deployment, and entails more complex readout electronics. Smaller occupied areas can be an important advantage of a smaller number of electrodes, especially in the case of children and shorter muscles. Therefore, we propose the use of standard disposable pre-gelled Ag/AgCl electrodes in a three-electrode setup, but it should be noted that our system supports all electrode types that can be connected to a 3.5 mm audio jack. It is also important to briefly describe possible challenges with drift due to user variability: the variations in electrode positioning between sessions or different users, different skin moisture, and movement artifacts.

Lines from measurement electrodes are equipped with diodes and RC circuits for transient voltage suppression (TVS) blocks. The following pre-amplifier (instrumentation amplifier) produces a single-ended voltage signal, which is then filtered with a high pass (HP) filter to remove DC component of the signal and amplified with a non-inverting amplifier to better fit the dynamic range of the analog-to-digital converter (ADC). Before sampling, the signal is centered in the middle of the ADC voltage reference and limited in spectrum to prevent aliasing by filtering with a bandpass filter (HP followed by low pass - LP). The cutoff frequencies (f_c) of all filters are indicated in Fig. 1(a), while the filter details and amplitude characteristics are shown in Fig. 1(b). The lower cutoff frequency of the bandpass filter (0.16 Hz) is set to remove very low-frequency components, including baseline caused by movement artifacts and breathing. The upper cutoff of 1560 Hz is chosen to eliminate high-frequency interferences. The choice of 0.16 Hz–1560 Hz for the bandpass filter was a compromise designed to minimize noise while retaining most of the useful signal for our intended application. The HP filter is realized as a passive RC filter (first order: $R = 1 \text{ M}\Omega$ and $C = 1 \mu\text{F}$), while the LP filter is the 3rd order and formed as a cascade of a Sallen-Key filter topology (2nd order) and a first order passive RC filter ($R = 2.2 \text{ k}\Omega$ and $C = 0.22 \mu\text{F}$). The reason for selecting these filter topologies is primarily based on simplicity, cost-effectiveness, high noise rejection and a non-inverting gain [34].

Finally, the output of EMG AFE is connected to the ADC for sampling. The resolution of the ADC depends on the implemented type (external or internal of the microcontroller) and the specific model. Therefore, the ADC resolution of our system will be reported in subsection 3.2. The operation of the ADC and other peripherals (battery charger and BLE controller) is controlled by the microcontroller, as shown in Fig. 1(a). The proposed microcontroller is the nRF52840 microcontroller (32-bit ARM Cortex-M4 CPU with an operating frequency of 64 MHz) from Nordic Semiconductor. The nRF52840 includes protocol support for BLE, a floating-point unit and an embedded 12-bit ADC. Reports indicate that when there is no obstruction between the nRF52840 and the smartphone, the average distance at which BLE data exchange is possible is about 100 m [35]. The proposed EMG analog front end is based on MCP609 operational amplifiers (a gain bandwidth product (GBWP) of 155 kHz and minimal Common Mode Rejection Ratio (CMRR) 75 dB) and MAX6106 voltage reference (with a temperature coefficient of 75 ppm/ $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and regulation accuracy of $\pm 0.4 \%$), while LP and HP filters are implemented as RC circuits [36]. An amplifier with common-mode rejection driven right leg is proposed for efficient power line noise rejection. There are also other possibilities for the realization

of EMG AFE, such as use of AD8221 or integrated front-end systems (e. g., MAX30001 and MAX30004), which may be favored in cases where high precision is needed in the presence of a high noise level, while MCP609 may be preferred if low power consumption and low cost are primary considerations.

As the system is battery powered, there is also a resistive voltage divider circuit to monitor the battery voltage. The microcontroller will enable/disable battery charging based on battery voltage measurement. Resistances of resistors are in mega ohm range to ensure low current draw from the battery. It is assumed that the microcontroller will be powered at 3.3 V; otherwise, if supply voltage and input-output logic are 5 V, the voltage divider will not be needed. However, a voltage booster would be needed to power devices with 5 V logic from the single rechargeable Li-Po battery, or more batteries in series (which would require a balancing circuit for efficient charging). The battery charger is based on BQ25101 made by Texas Instruments [37]. Charging current can be selected in the range from 10 mA to 250 mA, which follows the request that charging current is no higher than $C/10$, where C is the battery capacitance (we propose use of 1000 mAh Li-Po). In the event of BLE signal loss, data security will be ensured through storage on the on-board micro-SD memory card.

3.3. EMG signal processing

Due to the possibility to have inherent variations and drift in baseline EMG amplitudes among different individuals, the first step in the proposed EMG processing is normalization which includes subtraction of voltage baseline x_{baseline} (the middle of ADC voltage reference) from the measured EMG voltage x_{raw} . EMG signals can change polarity during different muscle contractions. By taking the absolute value, consistent interpretation and comparison of muscle activity across different conditions or subjects becomes possible. Because of that, values obtained from the normalization step are rectified (converted to their absolute values). Finally, smoothing (moving average filter with a sliding window-first in, first out) is performed:

$$x_{\text{filtered}}[n] = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{k=0}^{M-1} |x_{\text{raw}}[n-k] - x_{\text{baseline}}| \quad (1)$$

where M is the window size, input signal is x_{raw} and output x_{filtered} . Processing steps are illustrated in Fig. 1(c). The main advantages of the sliding window approach are: (1) nearly real-time computation as new samples are received, (2) the sliding window is memory efficient as it allows continuous updating without storing the entire signal history, and (3) it provides a more meaningful representation of muscle activation over time (by the extraction of the envelope of the signal). When compared to more complicated filtering methods, the implemented moving average filter does not suffer from limitations such as phase distortions and ringing artifacts (high-order filters e.g. Butterworth), complex determination of optimal filter coefficients (finite and infinite impulse response filters), time-frequency trade-off (wavelet transform [38]), the requirement for a training period to learn the dynamics of the signal (adaptive filters), and so on. Moreover, some finite impulse response filters can be sensitive to outliers, especially if using a small filter kernel (which is very common when fast data processing is needed).

The similarity of two signals can be determined in two primary ways: frequency-domain analysis (Discrete Time Short-Time Fourier Transform, or coherence analysis, etc.) or time-domain analysis (Wavelet transform, amplitude-based similarity, dynamic time warping, and similar). However, frequency-domain methods require more computational power, leading to latency. This can be a challenge for real-time applications, especially on embedded hardware-based platforms, where optimizations may be needed to ensure responsiveness. For instance, the straightforward multiplication of smoothed amplitudes from two signals can be misleading. This becomes evident in scenarios

where the product of a large value and a small signal value equals the product of two medium signal values. Such occurrences can distort data interpretation, potentially obscuring meaningful patterns. In the case of EMG signals, it is necessary to implement a method that directly measures the similarity of signals in terms of their amplitude scale and time alignment. Our approach to address this task is the use of cross-correlation. The mathematical expression for circular cross-correlation R_{x_1, x_2} calculation of two discrete signals ($x_1[n]$ and $x_2[n]$) for the window size N over lag m is given with:

$$R_{x_1, x_2}[m] = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x_1[n] \cdot x_2[(n+m) \bmod N] \quad (2)$$

The main reason for using circular cross-correlation instead of linear cross-correlation lies in the fact that we observed advantages and higher accuracy in on-the-fly calculations, which was also reported earlier in Ref. [39]. To perform on-the-fly cross-correlation of two input arrays as new samples are coming in, we implemented a sliding window approach. A window of size N with the most recent samples (first in, first out) for both arrays (x_1 and x_2) is maintained, and the cross-correlation value is updated as new samples arrive.

Window sizes of M (for filtering) and N (for cross-correlation calculation) can be selected with respect to various criteria. Our hypothesis is that the window size of moving average filter should be determined with respect to the typical duration of muscle activity for the given application, because short windows do not significantly contribute to signal cleaning from noise, while higher values introduce lag and decrease of EMG amplitude, as it will be shown in subsection with the simulation results. Therefore, our selection of equal window sizes of M and N is based on simulation analysis and verified with experimental results with a very fast and reliable response.

3.4. Simulation analysis

Aiming to analyze the performances of the proposed approach for EMG signal processing, we also created a MATLAB-based simulation. We utilized a publicly available EMG signal sampled at 4 kHz and with a duration of nearly 12 s (emg_healthy.txt) from PhysioNet [40] for the simulations analysis, enabling the comparison and reproducibility in future works by other authors. EMG signal is first rectified and then smoothed using a sliding window moving average filter with a varying window size). Subsequently, the cross-correlation between the processed EMG signals is calculated using a circular buffer with varying window sizes. The targeted outcome of the simulation analysis was to determine the procedure for the configuration of window size of moving average and cross-correlation calculations, as well as to demonstrate suitability of the proposed device architecture for the targeted application (registration of human muscles contractions and determination of muscle similarity responses).

The second goal of the simulation analysis was to perform comparison of our proposed approach with the Morlet Wavelet Transform (MWT) [41] and Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) [42], with respect to the processing time, selectivity and accuracy in the determination of similarity in EMG signals.

The MWT is described with:

$$MWT[n, s] = e^{j2\pi \cdot 6n} \cdot e^{-\frac{n^2}{2s^2}} \quad (3)$$

where n represents the discrete time variable, while s is the scale parameter. The range of scales was set to the window size that was used for the cross-correlation calculations. Smoothed and rectified EMG signals are then convoluted with MWT at different scales. The absolute values of resulting coefficients are then multiplied element by element. After summing over scales, the values are normalized to a range between 0 and 1 by division with the maximum calculated value. A similarity threshold was set to 0.8, and frequencies exceeding this threshold are

identified.

DTW similarity between two signals was calculated using a sliding window approach. The distance d between signals x_1 and x_2 was calculated based on the cache matrix D as:

$$d = D(n_{x_1} + n_{x_2}) \quad (4)$$

where n_{x_1} and n_{x_2} are the number of rows in signals x_1 and x_2 , while D is calculated for the specific window w (the same window size as for cross correlation and MWT):

$$D[i+1, j+1] = \text{norm}(x_1(i, :) - x_2(j, :)) + \min\{D(i, j+1), D(i+1, j), D(i, j), D(i, j-w+1), \dots, D(i, j+w)\} \quad (5)$$

where i and j iterate over the rows of signals x_1 and x_2 , respectively, while Euclidean norm is marked with *norm*. For each window position, segments are extracted from both signals, and the DTW distance is computed using the efficient implementation provided by Wang [43]. The DTW distance is then transformed into a similarity measure using a decreasing function:

$$DTW \text{ distance} = \frac{1}{1+d} \quad (6)$$

The resulting similarity values (*DTW distance*) are stored in an array, providing a measure of similarity between corresponding segments of the two signals for each window position.

3.5. Smartphone application

The smartphone application is developed using MIT App Inventor. After starting up, the developed smartphone application utilizes BLE scanning functionality to search for nearby BLE devices, retrieves their MAC addresses, and compiles a list to display the discovered BLE devices on the user interface. A proper MAC address should be selected, and communication will be established. The smartphone application has routines to connect to the specific service (defined by the microcontroller code) and four characteristics (Battery voltage, EMG Channel 1, EMG Channel 2, and Cross-Correlation value). The smartphone acts as the central, while the microcontroller is a peripheral. The battery voltage value is read only at the start up, while the other three characteristics are regularly updated. If a system operates with single EMG channel, then one BLE characteristic is the defined sequence of contractions/relaxations that muscle should follow. There are also two blocks for real-time data presentation: numerical and graphical, as shown in Fig. 1(d).

3.6. Microcontroller programming code

The microcontroller programming code is written in Arduino Integrated Development Environment (IDE), which is a framework built on top of the C++ programming language. Like other programs written in Arduino IDE, our program consists of two main loops: *init(2)* and *loop(2)*, as shown in Fig. 1(e).

The first loop is for initialization purposes. Initially, we enable serial port communication through the USB (when a PC-based station is connected for program code updates, debugging or data retrieval). Next, we activate BLE (with the microcontroller acting as a peripheral in BLE transmissions), set the name of the BLE device (visible to others), define the advertised service, set characteristics, and add the service to BLE. Finally, we set the initial values of characteristics to zero.

The second loop runs continuously and consists of one main module: it listens for BLE central devices and checks if a central device is connected. Once connected, the microcontroller retrieves its MAC address, and determines whether data should be sent (to prevent unauthorized access to data). If data transmission is required, several actions are taken. ADC samplings of connected EMG channels are performed,

followed by their basic processing (as described in section 3.2) and cross correlation calculations of EMG envelopes. The corresponding BLE characteristics are then updated. Continuous assessment of signals from EMG channels' similarity in real-time is ensured by dynamical computing cross-correlation as new data arrives, updating buffers, and promptly utilizing the results.

3.7. Testing and experimental validation procedures

Our developed device can perform three main functions: (1) reliable collection of EMG data from one or two channels, (2) determining if the muscle of interest followed the predefined profile of contractions/relaxations, and (3) performing cross-correlation analysis to determine if both muscles were simultaneously activated. Therefore, the testing and validation procedure is performed with the aim to validate all three functionalities (later labelled as Validation Phase 1, Validation Phase 2 and Validation Phase 3). EMG signals with human volunteers were collected using the developed system and the reference device (Biopac Lab MP36). Volunteers signed informed consent to participate. The Commission for the Ethics of Clinical Research (University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad, Serbia) gave consent for the implementation of the research (Number: 01-39/239/1, date: October 5th, 2022).

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Results of the simulation analysis: performance analysis of the proposed method and comparison with Morlet Wavelet Transform (MWT) and dynamic time warping (DTW)

A time domain representation of the PhysioNet EMG signal is shown in Fig. 2(a), while the results of the MATLAB-based Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) analysis are shown in Fig. 2(b). The inset of Fig. 2(b) shows the FFT of the experimentally obtained EMG signal using commercial device (as presented in subsection 4.4) and indicates a very similar frequency content and amplitude ratio. The resulting FFT is then processed to compute the two-sided spectrum, which is subsequently

normalized by the signal length. The relevant positive frequency components are extracted, and their amplitudes are doubled to account for the symmetric nature of the FFT output, deriving the single-sided spectrum. The obtained FFT is further processed to determine the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). The SNR is calculated based on the maximum signal power and the mean noise power derived from the adjusted power spectrum (with excluded DC component). The calculated SNR was 15.08 dB, which falls within the typical range for EMG systems (5 dB–20 dB) [44]. As will be shown later in subsection 4.4, very similar results in terms of the signal shape and spectral content were experimentally obtained with the developed device. However, it is also important to implement more complex and accurate simulation models of EMG, including cylindrical descriptions of the volume conductor [45] or corresponding force signal in skeletal muscles [46]. This will be addressed in future work.

EMG signals are rectified and smoothed using a sliding window moving average filter with a varying window size. For easier comparison with muscle activity duration, the window size was mapped to the corresponding time duration. An example of EMG signals with variations in intensity and duration of muscle activity are shown in Fig. 2(c). Smoothed signals are also shown in Fig. 2(c). Window size varied from 0.1 s to 0.5 s. Lower values did not significantly contribute to signal cleaning from noise, while higher values introduced lag and decrease of EMG amplitude, as shown in Fig. 2(d). This effect is less pronounced when muscle contraction is longer in duration. Therefore, the rationale for selecting the window size for moving average filtering can be $\leq 10\%$ of the typical duration of muscle contraction, which we will apply in further tests and experimental implementation.

Subsequently, the cross-correlation between the processed EMG signals (Fig. 3(a)) is calculated using a circular buffer with varying window sizes. The window size of cross correlation was equalized to the window size of the smoothing filter and then decreased by 10 %, 20 %, 30 % and 40 %. Calculated values have smaller intensity with shorter window size, which might be a disadvantage in the case of lower EMG amplitudes. On the other hand, longer window sizes do not introduce longer delays in the response. Additionally, the method could detect muscle contractions in a very short time, as shown in Fig. 3(b).

Fig. 2. (a) The domain representation of the PhysioNet EMG signal, (b) the FFT analysis of the PhysioNet EMG signal (c) the rectified PhysioNet EMG signal, and (d) the impact of varying window size of moving average for smoothing of PhysioNet EMG signal that is shown in (a).

Fig. 3. (a) and (c) The analyzed EMG signals; (b) and (d) the impact of varying window size of cross-correlation on similarity estimation of two EMG signals.

Therefore, our rationale for selecting the optimal value of window size for cross-correlation calculations is to equalize it to the size of moving average filter, based on the typical muscle duration for the given application.

For comparison with the proposed method, a similarity analysis of EMG signals was also determined using the MWT and DTW. Analysis was performed on many datasets, with representative examples of generated EMG signals shown in Fig. 4(a) and (c). Fig. 4(a) and (b) show the overlap of EMG signals (column labelled as the first case), while Fig. 4(d) and (e) show the shift to the right of the second signal when compared to the first signal (column labelled as the second case). It is evident from Fig. 4(c) (which presents calculated similarities of signals from Fig. 4(a) and (b)) and Fig. 4(f) (which presents calculated similarities of signals from Fig. 4(d) and (e)) that all three methods can be used to determine signal similarities. Values of normalized similarities closer to 1.0 indicate strong similarity, while values close to zero indicate weak similarity. The limitation of our implementation of the DTW method is that it cannot eliminate signals' similarity while there are no contractions, as seen in Fig. 4(c). Therefore, even though it is possible, the unsupervised functionality of the DTW seems to be limited. Our implementation of the MWT-based similarity provided better selectivity than DTW, but it was wider than the actual match of EMG signals. Finally, processing of those EMG signals with the three methods was compared with the goal of determining the execution time. The analysis was performed offline with a total data duration of 12 s (signal was down sampled to 1 kHz). Therefore, 12 thousand samples were processed per epoch using MATLAB 2013b installed on Dell G5 laptop (core i7, 9th generation, 2.6 GHz clock and 16 GB of RAM). The cross-correlation and MWT had similar execution times, while DTW-based similarity was slightly slower. From the conducted analysis, a

conclusion that cross-correlation based similarity acts as the most suitable and reliable approach for implementation on low-complexity embedded-hardware platforms can be made. Additionally, it can be noticed that the proposed processing method is capable of nearly real-time computations (less than 0.8 s is needed to process 12 s of data).

4.2. Developed hardware and software prototype

The hardware outcome of the proposed circuit topology is shown in Fig. 5(a) and (b). The overall dimensions are 90 mm × 60 mm × 9 mm. The primary design and realization considerations were not focused on a high level of integration, but on ensuring modularity and achieving a balanced spatial distribution. Modularity allows for the selection of either single or dual EMG readout, which can reduce costs if only a single EMG recording is needed. Additionally, comparable dimensions and weight of the PCBs and battery were prioritized to provide a balanced spatial distribution. We used standard disposable pre-gelled ECG Ag/AgCl electrodes (51 mm × 33 mm) from Ceracarta, as shown in Fig. 5(c). The screenshot of the developed smartphone application is shown in Fig. 5(d). The first graph shows measured EMG signals, while the bottom shows the calculated value of cross correlation.

The maximum sampling time can be dependent on the implementation of the function for access to ADC registers. In case of using Arduino IDE and embedded function *analogRead*, we obtained a mean ± standard deviation $579.77 \mu\text{s} \pm 66.86 \mu\text{s}$ for 1000 times repeated single channel ADC readings, which corresponds to the sampling frequency of 1.72 kHz. The corresponding values in case of dual channel ADC readings were $624.94 \mu\text{s} \pm 54.68 \mu\text{s}$ and sampling frequency of 1.6 kHz.

Fig. 4. (a) and (b) EMG signal used in the first analysis, (c) calculated similarities of three methods for the first case; (d) and (e) EMG signal used in the second analysis, (f) calculated similarities of three methods for the first case.

4.3. The power consumption analysis

The power profiler for nRF52840's BLE enables the calculation of current consumption for various operating conditions [47]. For the configuration of BLE peripheral (4 BLE characteristics with 4-byte float data type), the corresponding transmitting payload per event is 16 bytes, while the corresponding Link Layer Protocol Data Unit (LL PDU) is 27 bytes. Therefore, the BLE event length is about 2.5 ms, as shown in Fig. 6 (a). Total average current is 49 μ A for the transmitting power of -40 dBm, and 73 μ A for +8 dBm. In the remaining text of this subsection, all current consumption values are given for the highest transmitting level of +8 dBm. The duration of the pre-processing phase is 60 μ s, requiring a current of 4.0 mA. The next phase is crystal ramp-up with duration of 400 μ s and current consumption of 1.6 mA. During the standby phase, the system operates with a current consumption of 0.5 mA over a duration of 1072 μ s. The start radio phase requires 3.2 mA over the period of 130 μ s, while the radio receiving phase lasts 88 μ s with current consumption of 6.1 mA. The radio switch operation (to transmission phase) requires 3.5 mA over the period of 140 μ s. The radio transmitting operation requires the highest current (15.1 mA) over a period of 208 μ s. The final post processing phase has a duration of 350 μ s with a

current consumption of 2.0 mA.

The power consumption of the developed system based on nRF52840 microcontroller board was measured using E5270B Measurement Mainframe [Fig. 6(b)]. The program code of the microcontroller was not changed over time, but the configuration of the EMG AFE and BLE radio was varied to perform the characterization of these subsystems. The microcontroller-board without connected EMG AFE and with an established connection with the BLE central (smartphone with installed application), consumed an average current of 1.25 mA, as shown in Fig. 6(c). The addition of EMG AFE increased the average current consumption to 7.7 mA [Fig. 6(d)]. The obtained results for the system with full functionality, shown in Fig. 6(e), clearly indicate a good match with the theoretical power consumption of BLE transmissions. With the established connection with BLE central, the average current consumption increased to 20.5 mA, while spikes with a typical current of 15 mA are visible during periodical BLE transmissions. It should be noted that the sampling time of the used measurement system was not configurable for a finer time step, which would enable validation of theoretical power consumption profile [Fig. 6(a)]. The measured spikes are not equal due to the same reason, the inherent limitations of the fixed sampling time, which prevented a more precise capture of variations in

Fig. 5. (a) The hardware prototype of the developed system, (b) battery powered operation and indication of on-board micro SD card memory for data storage in case of BLE link disruption, (c) placement of electrodes for EMG signal acquisition, (d) the screenshot of the developed smartphone application.

Fig. 6. (a) Theoretical power profiler for nRF52840's BLE, (b) E5270B-based measurement setup, (c) power consumption of the microcontroller board without EMG AFE and without BLE transmissions, (d) power consumption of the microcontroller board with EMG AFE and without BLE transmissions, and (e) the measured current consumption of the developed system with BLE transmissions.

the power consumption profile. Because of that, we extended the sampling period to 15 s. The obtained results (average current consumption of 20.5 mA) suggest that more than 2 days of continuous and non-stop operation are possible with the fully charged battery that we used (Li-Po with the capacity of 1000 mAh).

4.4. Validation phase 1: comparison with reference device and monitoring of different muscle activation levels

Initially, a validation study was conducted using single-channel EMG signals obtained with the developed device and the reference device

(Biopac Lab MP36). The volunteer (male, 27-years-old) was instructed to perform a set of 5 contractions (with a duration of 2 s and with approximately the same intensity) and relaxations (with a duration of 3 s). Biopac Lab MP36 was connected to the laptop through the USB cable, while the laptop was running the Biopac Student Lab 4.1 software for signal acquisition and visualization. A signal gain of 200 was set for Biopac Lab MP36, while no other signal processing methods were applied. Both devices were set to have sampling frequency of 1 kHz. The experimental setup and obtained results are shown in Fig. 7(a) and (b), respectively. It may be seen that both devices successfully recorded muscle activities. However, it is important to note that voltage

Fig. 7. (a) Experimental setup for Biopac Lab MP36, (b) obtained EMG voltages with Biopac Lab MP36 and with the developed device, (c) spectral analysis of collected EMG signals, (d) the ADC samples of single channel EMG recordings with the proposed device, and (e) the processed EMG signal with the developed device clearly indicates different intensities and duration of muscle activities.

amplitudes in the case of the Biopac were slightly higher during both phases, indicating higher amplification of the signal. However, Biopac exhibited drift, which was not noticed with the developed device. When compared to the maximal volunteer contraction (MVC), which occurred at the fifth contraction, all contractions had a similar intensity of 0.8–1.0 of relative intensity. The FFT is applied in MATLAB to convert the obtained time-domain signals into the frequency domain, and generated single-sided spectrums are shown in Fig. 7(c). The magnitude of frequency components is lower in the case of the developed device, but both spectrums revealed similar content. The obtained FFTs are further processed with the aim of determining the SNR of both devices. The calculated SNR of Biopac was 17.44 dB, while for the developed device SNR was 10.73 dB. Despite our system having a lower SNR, it should be noted that both values are within the range 5 dB–20 dB of typical EMG systems [44].

In the second step, we captured responses with the developed device from the forearm muscle under different intensities and durations. Examples of recorded signals showcasing the variability in intensities and durations of six contractions are presented in Fig. 7(d). Subsequently, the raw EMG signal underwent the proposed processing, resulting in the EMG signal illustrated in Fig. 7(e), which clearly indicates variations in both intensity and duration. With simple thresholding, it is possible to differentiate contractions with a certain relative intensity when compared to the MVC, as shown in Fig. 7(e) with the threshold set to 20 %.

4.5. Validation phase 2: muscle activity evaluation (analysis of EMG response against the predefined sequence of contractions/relaxations)

To further assess the performance of the single-channel EMG recordings from forearm muscle contractions/relaxations, an analysis was conducted against a predefined sequence involving a 1.5-s contraction followed by a 2-s relaxation. The smartphone with the installed application was given to the subject, with the instruction to follow the sequence generated on the main screen (as may be seen in the video provided as supplementary material). The subject’s reactions to this sequence were successfully recorded, as illustrated in Fig. 8(a) and (b). Occasionally, the subject was instructed to deviate from the sequence, resulting in instances of missed target profiles, rather than indicating system unresponsiveness. The cross-correlation calculations, depicted in Fig. 8(c), can be used as a clear indicator of success in following the given sequence, with all 13 matches accurately registered. The average sampling time for this analysis was approximately 33.86 ms, reflecting an increase due to the additional processing required to handle the EMG signal, generate the target profile, and calculate cross-correlation values. Execution time can be significantly reduced if the mobile phone application takes on the tasks of EMG signal processing, which is marked as our future work.

4.6. Validation phase 3: muscle symmetry index

The final stage of validation involved dual EMG recordings from the forearms of both hands. The subject followed instructions to produce

Fig. 8. (a) The ADC samples of single channel EMG recordings with predefined sequence that should be followed; (b) comparisons of the processed EMG signal with predefined sequence; and (c) cross-correlation calculations clearly indicate when the muscle activity followed the given sequence.

different responses: simultaneous contraction of muscles in both hands, contractions only on the left/right hand with the muscles on the right/left side relaxed, as depicted in Fig. 9(a). The processed EMG signals clearly reveal stronger contractions in the right hand of the subject (Fig. 9(b)), and the cross-correlation analysis (Fig. 9(c)) confirmed the system's ability to detect whether muscles in both hands were active simultaneously (all four instances were registered). The average sampling time experienced a slight increase to about 33.90 ms.

4.7. EMG-based monitoring of forearm exercises of human volunteers

Five volunteers were included in the study of EMG-based monitoring of forearm exercises. Similar sample sizes are typical in related works, such as 5 [29], or just two [26]. Subjects 1, 2, 4 and 5 were males, aged 34 ± 6 , while Subject 3 was a 41-year-old female. Volunteers followed the procedure described in validation phase 2 (subsection 3.5). The predefined sequence ran on the developed mobile phone application, with simultaneous presentation of the set sequence and their muscle activity, as presented in the supplementary video. Two tests, each lasting 60 s, were performed. As shown in Fig. 10, all five subjects demonstrated much better success in the second test, which is promising for the implementation of the developed system in rehabilitation purposes. This indicates that guided users are more likely to follow the target sequence successfully with increased proficiency after just two sessions, and an expected increase in proficiency in subsequent sets. An important observation from these tests was that the system did not require baseline or drift correction among volunteers with different sexes and ages.

4.8. Key performance indicators and comparison with relevant works from the literature

In subsection 4.2 we presented the main features of the proposed system, followed by device validation for suitability for EMG data collection and guidance through the muscle activity are presented. Before conclusion, we gave the comparison of key performance indicators of our system with the relevant works from the literature in Table 1. It is important to note that realizations of systems with EMG feedback were of interest, rather than systems for advanced EMG data

collection. While not all works reported the performance indicators of interest, Table 1 illustrates that our system aligns with current technological achievements. It should be noted that an increase in EMG channels can be easily made as bearing in mind that microcontroller nRF52840 has 6 available ADC channels. Despite a slightly lower sampling frequency compared to some works, that does not present important limitation to the planned purpose, in which muscle responses are in close to being measured in seconds. The addition of external ADC will increase sampling frequency and ADC resolution; however, it will increase the price of the system. In summary, our work stands out due to a balanced set of specifications and overall cost. The inclusion of *in-situ* cross-correlation-based similarity analysis makes it a valuable tool for real-time EMG-based treatments, monitoring in recovery after injuries, and better success in fitness.

Therefore, this research presents a cost-effective, portable EMG feedback system that integrates *in-situ* cross-correlation-based algorithm for real-time muscle activation evaluation, a feature not commonly found in existing systems. Unlike other systems that rely on external computational resources or post-processing (e.g., MATLAB-based systems), our device supports real-time, on-device processing, making it suitable for home use. Additionally, our system is designed to be scalable, supporting up to six EMG channels, and includes BLE connectivity and a mobile app for user-friendly, continuous monitoring. We have validated our system through experimental work with human volunteers, demonstrating reliable EMG acquisition and signal processing. These innovations and practical benefits distinguish our work from existing solutions, offering significant advancements in the field of EMG feedback systems.

5. Conclusion

The developed device, equipped with two EMG channels sampled at 12-bit resolution and a sampling frequency of up to 1.6 kHz, exhibits the capacity for muscle monitoring across various clinical contexts. By implementing an algorithm for dynamic *in-situ* real-time muscle response evaluation, the system enables analysis of whether subjects adhere to predefined muscle contraction and relaxation profiles. The integration of wireless connectivity (BLE-based) enables remote

Fig. 9. (a) The ADC samples of dual channel EMG recordings; (b) comparisons of the processed EMG signal of both channels; and (c) cross-correlation calculations clearly indicate when forearm muscles of both hands were activated at the same time.

Fig. 10. Results of EMG-based monitoring of forearm exercises for three human volunteers: (a) the first test for Subject 1, (b) the second test for Subject 1, (c) comparison of cross calculations for two tests in case of Subject 1, (d) the first test for Subject 2, (e) the second test for Subject 2, (c) comparison of cross calculations for two tests in case of Subject 2, (g) the first test for Subject 3, (h) the second test for Subject 3, (i) comparison of cross calculations for two tests in case of Subject 3, (j) the first test for Subject 4, (k) the second test for Subject 4, (l) comparison of cross calculations for two tests in case of Subject 4, (m) the first test for Subject 5, (n) the second test for Subject 5, (o) comparison of cross calculations for two tests in case of Subject 5.

assessment of EMG activities, offering utility in fitness scenarios when trainers monitor athlete’s activities, or medical doctors observe patients performing exercises during recovery after injuries or in UI treatment. Additionally, its small dimensions, lightweight properties, and rechargeable battery-based powering render this device wearable, making it valuable for home applications of EMG feedback in treating

various conditions.

Main limitations of the proposed system arise from the targeted goal of cost-effectiveness and achievement of the minimal requirements needed for reliable EMG data collection and *in-situ* processing. The use of dual EMG sensing may not suffice for certain applications such as spatial monitoring of diaphragm activities [48] or automated recognition of

Table 1
Key Performance Indicators and comparison with the literature.

Reference, year	This work	[29], 2021	[30], 2023	[31], 2015	[32], 2019	[33], 2020
Parameter						
EMG Channels	2 (up to 6)	1	1	1	1	2
Sampling frequency	up to 1.6 kHz	NR	2.5 kHz	10 kHz (NI USB 6009)	1 kHz	NR
ADC resolution	12-bit	NR	12-bit	14-bit	12-bit	12-bit
Battery power/charger	Y/Y	Y/N	Y/NR	N	Y/Y	NR/NR
Wireless connection	BLE	Bluetooth	Bluetooth	N	BLE	BLE
Mobile phone app.	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	NR
<i>In-situ</i> muscle similarity index	Y	N	N	MATLAB-based	N	N
Predefined sequence	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N
Power consumption	20.5 mA @ 3.3V	110 mA @ 7.4 V	NR	NR	39.5 mA @ 3 V	NR
Dimensions	90 mm × 60 mm × 9 mm	55 mm × 115 mm × 10 mm	35 mm × 11 mm × 53 mm	NR	30 mm × 30 mm	20 mm × 65 mm

Y-Yes, N-No, NR-Not Reported.

hand gestures [49]). However, it adequately serves our intended purposes, including home recovery after injuries, enhancing fitness outcomes, and facilitating biofeedback-based treatments. Moreover, robot-assisted stroke recovery [8] or gesture recognition may demand more complex filters, such as synchro squeezing wavelet transform with differential evolution optimized threshold [38], or implementation of deep learning models [50], and machine learning algorithms [51]. However, our primary focus has been on *in-situ* and real-time signal processing, eliminating the need for external computational resources or post-processing. On the other hand, the implemented circuit topology supports the addition of up to four more ADC channels, enabling potential system expansions. It is worth noting that our system exhibits a lower SNR compared to high-end commercial systems like the Biopac Lab MP36.

Our future work aims to develop a cloud-based infrastructure for remote access and storage of measurement data. Additionally, we plan to optimize sampling time by transferring some signal processing tasks to the mobile phone application, thus reducing the workload of the microcontroller to measurement and BLE-based data transfer. Finally, we intend to conduct a clinical study involving patients with UI-related conditions to evaluate different exercise programs for the UI treatment. While the focus of this work was on the engineering aspect and realization of a reliable system, our upcoming research will center on finding the optimal program to address UI-related issues in collaboration with medical institutions.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Mitar Simić: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Goran M. Stojanović:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2024.102472>.

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